

ORGANIC PESTICIDES. PART I. PREPARATION OF SOME FLUORO-ARYLOXY FATTY ACIDS AND THEIR MERCURY DERIVATIVES

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Several fluoro-aryloxy fatty acids and their mercury derivatives have been prepared as a preliminary to evaluation of their pesticidal activity.

The present work has been undertaken with a view to synthesising aromatic fluorine compounds which might act as potential pest control chemicals. Very little work has been done in this field, and the only work reported is by Finger *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 94; Illinois State Geological Survey, Circ. 199, 1955). Some of these compounds exhibit a high fungicidal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and have subsequently found use in the treatment of cotton fabrics and wood for prevention of decay.

In this paper, fluoro-aryloxy fatty acids and their mercury derivatives have been prepared as it has earlier been observed by Sen and Joshi that similar unhalogenated compounds are effective as fungicides and plant growth regulators under different conditions of concentration (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 333; *J. Sci. Food Agr.*, 1952, 2, 526). The introduction of fluorine might therefore be presumed to enhance the toxicity of such compounds.

The fluoro-aryloxy fatty acids have been obtained as usual by condensing fluorophenols with halogenated fatty acids in presence of caustic soda solution (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 1555). *o*-Fluorophenol has been obtained from *o*-anisidine by the Balz-Schiemann reaction, while *p*-fluorophenol has been prepared by the same reaction from both *p*-anisidine and *p*-phenetidine due to limited quantities of either in our stock. The fluoro-aryloxy fatty acids have been mercurated by the method described by Friend ("Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. XI, Part I) and by Sen and Joshi (*loc. cit.*), and their mono-mercurated derivatives obtained.

The pesticidal activity of these compounds is under investigation and will be communicated in due course.

EXPERIMENTAL

o-Fluoroanisole was prepared by the method of English, Mead and Niemann (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 350) from *o*-anisidine (141 c.c.), yield 45 g. (53.4%), b.p. 70-75°/30-35 mm. Bennett *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1935, 57, 1821) report b.p. 157-59°.

o-Fluorophenol—*o*-Fluoroanisole (45 g.) was demethylated as usual and *o*-fluorophenol isolated as a colorless liquid, b.p. 70-80°/30 mm, yield 15 g. Bennett *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) report b.p. 151-52°.

p-Fluorophenetole was prepared similarly from *p*-phenetidine (60 c.c.), yield 36 g., b.p. 75-80°/80-85 mm. Suter *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 161) report b.p. 54°/7 mm.

p-Fluoroanisole was obtained from *p*-anisidine (40 g.) by the above method, yield 18 g. (44%), b.p. 155-57°. Adams *et al.* ("Organic Reaction", Vol. V, p. 212) report b.p. 156-57°.

p-Fluorophenol.—Both *p*-fluoroanisole (36 g.) and *p*-fluorophenetole (36 g.) were dealkylated as usual, respective yield and b.p. being 16 g. (22%) and 24 g. (28.5%) and 185-86° (Finger *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, report 185°).

α-Bromo-fatty Acids.—*α*-Bromopropionic and -butyric acids were prepared by heating freshly distilled dry acids with bromine in the presence of PCl₃ (Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", p. 421). Their boiling points correspond to those previously recorded.

Fluoro-aryloxy acids were prepared by heating the appropriate phenol (1M) with the halogenated fatty acid (1M) and caustic soda solution (2M) at 100° for 3 to 6 hours (*loc. cit.*). Some of the fluoro-aryloxy acids, which were obtained as oils, solidified on cooling. Others solidified when distilled under reduced pressure. These were characterised by determination of their neutralisation equivalents. The compounds obtained are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Fluoro-aryloxy acid.	M.P. (obs.)	B.P. (obs.)	M.P. or B.P. (lit.)	% Yield.	Neut. equiv.	
					Found.	Calc.
<i>o</i> -Fluoro-phenoxyacetic	138-39°	..	139°	77.0	169.9	170.0
<i>o</i> -Fluoro-phenoxypropionic	82-83°	..	..	84.2	182.5	184.0
<i>o</i> -Fluoro-phenoxybutyric	..	120-23°/ 70-80 mm	..	60.0	196.3	198.0
<i>p</i> -Fluoro-phenoxyacetic	105°	..	105°	54.9	169.8	170.0
<i>p</i> -Fluoro-phenoxypropionic	93-94°	170-75°/ 55-60 mm	..	71.0	182.8	184.0
<i>p</i> -Fluoro-phenoxybutyric	..	170-75°/ 55-60 mm	..	56.6	198.5	198.0

Mercuration of Fluoro-aryloxy Fatty Acids.—The fluoro-aryloxy acids were mercurated by the method of Friend (*loc. cit.*) and Sen and Joshi (*loc. cit.*) Either a mixture of equimolecular quantities of mercuric acetate in water and fluoro-aryloxy acid in dilute acetic acid or a mixture with yellow mercuric oxide (1M) in 50% acetic acid solution was heated on a water-bath till a sandy powder separated. In some cases the mixture was refluxed for 2 hours over a low flame. The time required for the reaction varied from 1 to 6 hours. The precipitate was filtered and repeatedly washed with boiling water, hot dilute acetic acid and hot alcohol.

All the compounds are insoluble in water, dilute acids and common organic solvents, and are stable to air and light. When boiled with HCl (conc.), these are decomposed to mercuric chloride and the corresponding fluoro-aryloxy acid.

This solution was diluted with water, and mercury estimated as mercuric sulphide by passing H₂S into it, followed by washing the precipitate repeatedly with CS₂, ethanol and ether to dissolve sulphur and organic impurities (Vogel, *loc. cit.*, p. 504). The results of the analysis indicated that mono-mercurated anhydride of fluoro-aryloxy fatty acids were formed. The following mercury derivatives have been prepared.

TABLE II

	M.P.	% Mercury.	
		Found.	Calc.
(1) F.C ₆ H ₅ .(—O.CH ₂ .CO ₂)—Hg (<i>o</i>)	230°	54.68	54.44
(2) F.C ₆ H ₅ .(—O.CH ₂ .CO ₂)—Hg (<i>p</i>)	> 250°	53.75	54.44
(3) F.C ₆ H ₅ .(—O.CH.CH ₂ CO ₂)—Hg (<i>o</i>)	* 120-23°	51.60	52.48
(4) F.C ₆ H ₅ .(—O.CH.CH ₂ CO ₂)—Hg (<i>p</i>)	* 125°	51.14	52.48
(5) F.C ₆ H ₅ .(—O.CH.C ₂ H ₅ CO ₂)—Hg (<i>o</i>)	* 123°	51.23	50.63
(6) F.C ₆ H ₅ .(—O.CH.C ₂ H ₅ CO ₂)—Hg (<i>p</i>)	* 164°	49.45	50.63

* The compounds partly melt and then decompose.

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